

Sample and Data Usage Policy for the Genomes Stream of the BGE Project

– A Community Guidance Document –

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Contact and Governance

Questions or concerns about the application of these best practice usage policy recommendations and guidelines should be directed to the ERGA Secretariat, secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org. The ERGA Executive Board holds the responsibility for mediation and resolution of any emerging issues, with reference to this policy and to broader community standards for good scientific practice.

Preamble – What is the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) Project?

The **Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) Project**¹ aimed to accelerate the use of genomic science to enhance understanding of biodiversity, monitor biodiversity change, and guide interventions to address its decline. The **BGE Project** comprised activities focused on DNA Barcoding (**Barcoding Stream**) and Reference Genome Generation (**Genomes Stream**) for eukaryotic species across Europe, bringing together two European networks: **iBOL Europe**² and the **European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA)**³. The **Genomes Stream** worked towards the establishment and implementation of large-scale biodiversity genomic data generation pipelines to accelerate the production and accessibility of reference-quality, complete genome sequences for species across a variety of European eukaryotic biodiversity that will support applications in the fields of biodiversity characterisation, conservation, and biomonitoring. The **Genomes Stream** focused on generating reference genomes for biodiversity hotspots, pollinators, and a selection of applied case studies, as well as for critical European biodiversity from samples provided by ERGA Community members.

Purpose – Who and What are These Guidelines Designed For?

This sample and data usage policy is designed to guide two primary community groups who may use and/or reuse samples collected or data generated within the framework of the **Genomes Stream** of the **BGE Project**: (i) researchers who received BGE support either as BGE members affiliated to a BGE partner institution⁴, as subcontracted BGE parties (case studies, bioblitzes, hotspots), or as BGE community sample providers, and (ii) other researchers not directly associated with the **BGE Project**.

These guidelines are designed to clarify the conditions for the use and/or reuse of data generated by the **BGE Project**, and of samples collected and registered as part of the **BGE Project**. Data may include sample or processing metadata, raw or processed sequencing data, as well as assemblies or annotations, produced by the **BGE Project**. Samples may include those collected and biobanked, as well as partially sequenced samples and those not selected for sequencing by the **BGE Project**.

While recognising that BGE-produced data made available through the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC, BioProject [PRJEB61747](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJEB61747))⁵ have no use restrictions or licensing requirements, this BGE usage policy is designed to foster adherence to best practices for the proper acknowledgement of sample providers and data producers. These guidelines set out recommendations on how to properly acknowledge the contributions of the **BGE Project** in any publications benefitting from BGE resources. They additionally detail the best practices for ensuring correct acknowledgements and authorships for **Genome Reports** that may be produced and published after the official end of the **BGE Project**.

¹ <https://biodiversitygenomics.eu/>

² <https://iboleurope.org/>

³ <https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>

⁴ <https://biodiversitygenomics.eu/the-project/network/>

⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB61747>

Summary – BGE Genomes Stream Sample and Data Usage Policy

- ★ **Two Primary BGE Resources:** (A) samples (either collected samples or leftover materials), and (B) data (raw and processed DNA and RNA sequencing data, metadata, assemblies, annotations).
- ★ **Two Primary Community Use Scenarios:** (A) for research purposes using or building on BGE-produced resources, and (B) for publishing the **Genome Report** for assemblies (and their annotations, if available).
- ★ **Two Primary Community Users:** (A) researchers who received BGE support either as BGE members affiliated to a BGE partner institution⁶, as subcontracted BGE parties, or as BGE community sample providers, and (B) other researchers not directly associated with the **BGE Project**.
- ★ **Two Primary Publication Requirements:** (A) for research use - to cite the **Genome Report** (if available), and (B) for **Genome Reports** - to invite individuals who were directly involved in collecting the samples and/or producing the data to join the authorship. Receivers of BGE support are to additionally include the project acknowledgement statement.

How to Use and Acknowledge BGE Samples & Data beyond the BGE Project

[#] Genome Report collections at [Research Ideas and Outcomes - RIO](#)⁷ or [Open Research Europe - ORE](#)⁸

^{\$} Contact the ERGA Secretariat, secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org, to identify the involved individuals

⁶ <https://biodiversitygenomics.eu/the-project/network/>

⁷ https://riojournal.com/topical_collection/280/

⁸ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/collections/bge>

Researchers Who Received Support From the BGE Project

BGE members affiliated to a BGE partner institution⁹, subcontracted BGE parties (case studies, bioblitzes, hotspots), or BGE community sample providers who use and/or reuse samples collected or data generated within the framework of the **Genomes Stream** of the **BGE Project** are expected to:

- ★ Correctly acknowledge the **BGE Project** (see template acknowledgement statements provided below) in scientific publications or related outputs such as web pages describing research results.
- ★ Properly recognise the contributions of sample providers and data producers in scientific publications by citing the relevant **Genome Report** publication(s), if available.
- ★ Invite individuals involved in collecting samples and/or producing data to join the authorship of the publication of a **Genome Report** (or a similar technical publication of assembly/annotation generation).

Researchers Not Directly Associated With the BGE Project

Others who use and/or reuse samples collected or data generated within the framework of the **Genomes Stream** of the **BGE Project** are expected to:

- ★ Properly recognise the contributions of sample providers and data producers in scientific publications by citing the relevant **Genome Report** publication(s), if available.
- ★ Invite individuals involved in collecting samples and/or producing data to join the authorship of the publication of a **Genome Report** (or a similar technical publication of assembly/annotation generation).

Examples of Potential Uses of BGE Project Samples and Data

The use of **BGE Project** samples to produce data, or of already-produced genome sequencing data, and/or genome assembly data, and/or genome annotation data, including RNA sequencing data, and/or sample metadata information, potentially in combination with genomic data produced by others:

- ★ As part of a scientific study or survey, e.g. analyses that include genome assemblies, and/or annotations, and/or transcriptome data from the **BGE Project**
- ★ To map genetic diversity, including calling single nucleotide polymorphisms, defining structural variants, or building pangenomes, e.g. using sequencing read data from the **BGE Project**
- ★ To produce a genome annotation, or an improved or alternative genome annotation, e.g. using transcriptome data, or samples to produce transcriptome data, from the **BGE Project**
- ★ To produce a genome assembly, or an improved or alternative genome assembly, e.g. using sequencing read data, or samples to produce additional read data, from the **BGE Project**

⁹ <https://biodiversitygenomics.eu/the-project/network/>

BGE Project Acknowledgement Statement Templates

– For researchers who received support from the BGE Project –

These statement templates pertain to BGE Project data, please see below for additional recommendations for the use of BGE Project samples

[1] General acknowledgement, required, e.g. for websites describing research results

Data included in this study (*) were generated by the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) Project, funded by Horizon Europe under the grant agreement number 101059492, co-funded by the Swiss Government and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

[2] Specific acknowledgement, required, e.g. for publications describing research results

Data included in this study (*) were generated by the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) Project (Grant no. 101059492), funded by Horizon Europe under the Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment call (REA.B.3); co-funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract numbers 22.00173 and 24.00054; and by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy's Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme.

(*) For both cases, either delete the parentheses completely to make a generic acknowledgement statement, or add in the parentheses a brief description of the datasets that were used and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) BioProject accession(s), e.g. "(PacBio long-read sequencing data for *Holothuria sanctori* [PRJEB77251])" or "(RNAseq transcriptome sequencing data for *Tarphius canariensis* [PRJEB76559] and *Leonhardella angulicollis* [PRJEB77401])" or "(Genome assembly of *Leviellus thorell* [PRJEB77916])".

(*) If several datasets need to be listed, consider instead listing them with their accessions in a supplementary file that can then be named in the parentheses, e.g. "(See Supplementary File X)".

In addition to the acknowledgement statement, for publications describing research results that include at least one BGE member amongst the co-authors, when the journal requires and/or allows authors to enter grant information as part of the submission process to be included in the publication's metadata, make sure to enter **Horizon Europe** (or nearest relevant equivalent) as the funder and the grant number: **101059492**

Citing BGE Project Genome Reports and Dataset Accessions

– For use and/or reuse of samples collected or data generated within the BGE Project –

Genome Report Citations, required, e.g. for publications describing research results

- ★ The **BGE Project** has produced **Genome Reports** that provide standardised technical descriptions of the production of reference genomes that are published in collections at [Research Ideas and Outcomes](#) - RIO¹⁰ or [Open Research Europe](#) - ORE¹¹.
- ★ Note that some **BGE Genome Reports** (or similar technical publications describing assembly and annotation generation) may be published in other journals, these are linked from the RIO collection as soon as possible after publication.
- ★ When samples or data that are described in these **Genome Reports** are used (see page 4 above for examples), the recommended best practice for proper acknowledgement of sample providers and data producers is to directly cite the relevant **Genome Report(s)** in any publications.
- ★ If you are unable to locate any published **Genome Report(s)** relevant to the used samples or data, please contact the ERGA Secretariat, secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org, to establish if there is a report, or if the report production is planned and/or has started.

Reporting Dataset Accessions, required, e.g. for publications describing research results

- ★ If there is no relevant **Genome Report** available to cite, researchers not directly associated with the **BGE Project** must simply follow standard methods and/or data availability reporting best practices required by most journals by listing the accessions of the resources/datasets used in their study (e.g. ENA BioSample, BioProject, Sequence Read Archive, Assembly accessions, Collection accessions, Collection names, Collection URLs, etc.).
- ★ As detailed above, researchers who received support from the **BGE Project** must additionally correctly acknowledge the **BGE Project** using the templates provided.

¹⁰ https://riojournal.com/topical_collection/280/

¹¹ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/collections/bge>

Specific Recommendations for Producing Genome Assemblies and Reports

– For specific use and/or reuse of samples collected or data generated within the BGE Project to produce genome assemblies and Genome Reports –

- ★ Before starting to produce a **Genome Report** for a BGE-produced assembly or an assembly that benefitted from using data or samples from the **BGE Project**, contact the ERGA Secretariat (secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org) to establish if report production is planned and/or has started.
- ★ These recommendations apply to the publication of a **Genome Report**, Genome Note, or similar technical description of how the reference genome was generated, where samples and/or sequencing data from the **BGE Project** were used to generate a genome assembly, or to produce an improved/alternative assembly, e.g. by combining with genomic data produced by others.
- ★ This applies when there is no relevant **Genome Report** to cite. It is designed to ensure the proper acknowledgement of sample providers and data producers from the **BGE Project**. If there is a relevant **Genome Report** available, then simply cite the **Genome Report** publication (as described above).
- ★ When producing a **Genome Report**, or an assembly with its accompanying **Genome Report**, make sure to follow the guidelines for coordinating the publication of genome reports and the recommendations for producing genome assemblies and reports, detailed below.

Guidelines for coordinating the publication of Genome Reports:

- ★ For **BGE Project** species where the genome assembly has been submitted to the ENA but no **Genome Report** has yet been produced, coordination of the writing and publication of the **Genome Report** remains the primary responsibility of the **BGE Project** team that generated the reference genome.
- ★ To facilitate the continued production and publication of **Genome Reports** after the end of the **BGE Project**, this responsibility may be transferred to another suitable group through consultation with the relevant parties supervised by the ERGA Secretariat. Part of the transfer of responsibility includes the mandate to ensure that the sample provider(s) and other individuals who were directly involved in producing and processing the BGE data to generate the assembly are invited to join the authorship team of the **Genome Report**.
- ★ For **Genome Reports** of assemblies produced independently of the **BGE Project** yet that used BGE data or samples, the team that generated the reference genome is responsible for coordinating the writing and publication of the **Genome Report**, as well as for communicating with the ERGA Secretariat (secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org) to ensure that the sample provider(s) and other individuals who were directly involved in producing and processing the BGE data are invited to join the authorship team.

Recommendations for producing genome assemblies and Genome Reports:

- ★ **Assemblies:** Use the ERGA Assembly Report ([EAR](#)¹²) quality control system to have the assembly peer-reviewed and approved before uploading it to the ENA.

- ★ **Assemblies:** Follow the [ERGA guidelines](#)¹³ for data submission to the ENA. When this is completed, contact the ERGA Secretariat (secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org) to add the genome assembly BioProject as a component BioProject of the most relevant ERGA umbrella BioProject, e.g. the ERGA Community BioProject ([PRJEB66264](#)¹⁴), or the ERGA-BGE BioProject ([PRJEB61747](#)¹⁵).

- ★ **Genome Reports:**
 - Examples can be found at the ERGA **Genome Report** Collections hosted at [Research Ideas and Outcomes](#) - RIO¹⁶ or at [Open Research Europe](#) - ORE¹⁷.
 - As detailed above, authors must invite individuals who were directly involved in collecting the samples and/or producing the BGE data to join the authorship of the **Genome Report** – contact the ERGA Secretariat, secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org, to identify the individuals to invite to join the authorship team.
 - Note that if at least one co-author is a BGE member affiliated to a BGE partner institution¹⁸ then the **Genome Report** can be published without charge at the ERGA-BGE ORE Collection.
 - Alternatively, the **Genome Report** can be preprinted and/or published at the ERGA RIO Collection, by submitting a PDF for preprinting or by using the provided ARPHA template to write the **Genome Report** and publish it in the ERGA RIO Collection (see the [guidelines](#)¹⁹).
 - Alternatively, the **Genome Report** can be published elsewhere, and then a request to be linked from the ERGA RIO collection can be submitted (see ¹² for details and watch this video to find out more about [Genome Reports for the ERGA Community](#)²⁰).

¹² <https://github.com/ERGA-consortium/EARs>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14924160>

¹⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB66264>

¹⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB61747>

¹⁶ https://rijournal.com/topical_collection/280/

¹⁷ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/collections/bge>

¹⁸ <https://biodiversitygenomics.eu/the-project/network/>

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15634244>

²⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pO6d2QcVoLg>

Additional Recommendations for the Use of BGE Project Samples

Parties planning to use BGE-collected samples are expected to inform the ERGA Secretariat of their intentions (secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org) so that duplicated efforts can be avoided and relevant parties can be appropriately informed. The ownership of these samples is governed by the Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs) between the sample providers (community, case studies, bioblitzes, hotspots) and the **BGE Project** sequencing centres (see Table 1 below) and the BGE-associated biobanks. The terms of use detailed in these MTAs must be adhered to at all times. Note these guidelines pertain to samples stored at sequencing centres of biobanks, not to morphological vouchers deposited in national or other collections.

These additional recommendations refer to biosamples from the **BGE Project** that have been collected and registered (with BioSample accessions) at the ENA, but that remain unsequenced or partially sequenced and stored at **BGE Project** sequencing centres, or BGE-associated biobanks such as those of the Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change²¹ and the Natural History Museum of Madrid²² (BGE bioblitz samples). The future use of these samples, including to generate genomic data, e.g. to support the assembly and/or annotation of a reference genome or to generate transcriptome data, must comply with these policy guidelines for the use and acknowledgement of BGE-collected samples. As detailed above, this includes:

- ★ Referencing the existing ENA BioSample accession(s) and associated metadata, following standard methods and/or data availability reporting best practices required by most journals to list the accessions of the resources/datasets used.
- ★ For researchers who received support from the **BGE Project**, explicitly acknowledge that the samples were collected through **BGE Project** activities by including the following adaptations of the project acknowledgement statement templates:
 - Websites, etc. – *Data included in this study were generated using samples provided by the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) Project, funded by Horizon Europe under the grant agreement number 101059492, co-funded by the Swiss Government and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).*
 - Publications etc. – *Data included in this study were generated using samples provided by the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) Project (Grant no. 101059492), funded by Horizon Europe under the Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment call (REA.B.3); co-funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract numbers 22.00173 and 24.00054; and by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy's Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme.*
- ★ As for the BGE resource usage described above, when publishing a **Genome Report**, Genome Note, or similar technical description of how a reference genome was generated, authors must invite individuals who were directly involved in collecting the samples to join the authorship of the **Genome Report** (contact the ERGA Secretariat, secretariat@erga-biodiversity.org, to identify the relevant individuals).

²¹ <https://leibniz-lib.de/en/research/research-centres/zmb/bonn-location/biobank.html>

²² <https://www.mncn.csic.es/en/colecciones/cientificas/tissues-and-dna-biobank>

Background Information – Overview of the BGE Genomes Stream Workflow

The **Genomes Stream** workflow for generating reference genomes and associated data started with the coordination of sampling in **Work Package 5 (WP5)**, with the subsequent handover of responsibilities to **Work Package 7 (WP7)** once samples were received by the assigned sequencing centres. Data generated by WP7 were submitted to the ENA (**BGE Project** partners were required to submit all data that passed quality control checks to the ENA). **Work Package 9 (WP9)** was then responsible for coordinating the generation of the genome assemblies (and annotations) and submitting the assemblies to the ENA. Additional genome assemblies and associated data were produced and made available through case studies developed as part of **Work Package 11 (WP11)** activities. Throughout this workflow, **Work Package 3 (WP3)** provided support to ensure the production line was as efficient and effective as possible, and to facilitate communication between **BGE Project** partners and the sample providers.

WP5 initiated communications with sample providers from the ERGA community, biodiversity hotspots, and the bioblitz teams, and supported sample providers to collect and complete all the necessary information (legal and ethical sampling, sample metadata manifest, etc.). **WP7** then assigned species to the **BGE Project** sequencing centre partner organisations (Table 1), and the responsibility of communicating with sample providers was handed over from **WP5** to the relevant **WP7** partner. MTAs between each sample provider and the relevant **BGE Project** partner were completed, either with or without transfer of ownership of the biological material, as necessary. **WP3** acted as an operational contact point to inform sample providers, including those from **WP11** case studies, of the progress through the genome generation workflow, and to answer questions or to redirect questions from sample providers to the relevant **BGE Project** partner.

Table 1. BGE Project sequencing centre organisation contact details

BGE Sequencing Centre Partner Organisation	Contact Details
CNAG, Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico	https://www.cnag.eu/contact , projectmanager@cnag.eu
GENOSCOPE, Centre National de Séquençage	https://www.france-genomique.org/contact/?lang=en
SANGER, Wellcome Sanger Institute	https://www.sanger.ac.uk/about/contact-us/ , tol-administrator@sanger.ac.uk
SCILIFELAB, National Genomics Infrastructure	https://www.scilifelab.se/units/ngi/ , support@ngisweden.se
UNIBA, University of Bari	https://elixir-italy.org/how-we-work/platforms/ , omics.elixir@cnr.it
UNIFI, University of Florence	https://www.bio.unifi.it/vp-30-laboratori.html , genomica.avanzata@bio.unifi.it
UiO, University of Oslo	https://www.mn.uio.no/ibv/english/research/infrastructure/facilities/life-science/sequencing/nsc/ , post@sequencing.uio.no

By the end of the **BGE Project** (official end date: 28.02.2026), sample providers were informed by **WP3** about the status of the species for which they had supplied samples. Afterwards, queries regarding any potential follow-up actions for species assigned to sequencing centres must be directed to the relevant centre using the contacts provided in Table 1. With some specific variations, the general genome assembly status categories at the end of the project can be described as:

- A.** The assembly was successfully generated and submitted to the ENA, possibly also with the genome annotation completed, and possibly also with the **Genome Report** published.
- B.** Some or all types of data were generated and submitted to the ENA, however, the quantity and/or quality of the data mean that a genome assembly could not be generated.
- C.** All attempts to generate data failed, and therefore, no data could be submitted to the ENA.
- D.** The species was ultimately not selected for genome sequencing.

By setting out clear procedures and expectations above, these recommendations aim to foster adherence to best practices for the proper recognition of sample providers and data producers. Taking into account the four genome assembly status categories, a recap of the main requirements:

Status A.

- When using a genome assembly, annotation, or any other data associated with the generation of this resource, the recommended best practice is to cite the relevant **Genome Report(s)** (if available), and for receivers of BGE support to additionally include the project acknowledgement statement.
- When there is no **Genome Report** publication, and there is an interest to produce one, the recommended best practice is to invite individuals who were directly involved in collecting the samples and producing the BGE data and assembly to join the authorship of the **Genome Report**.

Status B.

- When BGE-produced data are used, possibly with additional data from other sources, to generate an assembly, the recommended best practice is to report dataset accessions in any resulting publications, and for receivers of BGE support to additionally include the project acknowledgement statement.
- If a **Genome Report** is to be produced for such an assembly, the recommended best practice is to invite individuals who were directly involved in collecting the samples and producing the BGE data to join the authorship of the **Genome Report**.

Status C.

- If there were any leftover materials after failed attempts to generate data, these can be accessed from the biobank of the Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change²³, subject to MTA terms. If used, follow the recommendations for proper use and acknowledgements detailed above.

Status D.

- If the species was not selected for genome generation, the associated samples may be accessed from the biobank of the Natural History Museum of Madrid²⁴, subject to MTA terms. If used, follow the recommendations for proper use and acknowledgements detailed above.

²³ <https://leibniz-lib.de/en/research/research-centres/zmb/bonn-location/biobank.html>

²⁴ <https://www.mncn.csic.es/en/colecciones/cientificas/tissues-and-dna-biobank>

